

BIM, IOT AND BMS FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF BUILDINGS AND INFRASTRUCTURES. THE DIGITAL TWIN FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The evolution of BIM application is the Facility management for the digitalization of the Activity Construction. The BIM application became the opportunity to increase the safeguard of the city during its entire life cycle, starting from the knowledge of the actual conservation of the building and the prospective for the future use.

Starting from the analysis of the evolution of the IOT Control system, the CDE and the evolution of the application browser, the focus is to create a process to simulate activity construction in cities and infrastructures. The application will be oriented to different case studies using different software (e.g. Autodesk, Bentley). Issues related to the design of different systems making up the CIB technology (systems of control and management of systems, security, voice-data-images and computer science communication) and the most appropriate methodology to achieve a good intelligent management capacity are also addressed.

Starting from GIS and survey obtained with different methods, the student will develop the simulation of cities and infrastructures, including the activity construction too. The final purpose of the FM will be defined for the whole life-cycle of cities and infrastructures with reference to case studies.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-MohammadMeshkini-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/eyWuFPFsZ1g>

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